

```
install.packages("metafor")
library(metafor)
```

```
dataset <- escalc(measure="MD", m1i=Mean_Treatment, sd1i=SD_Treatment,
n1i=N_Treatment,
                m2i=Mean_Control, sd2i=SD_Control, n2i=N_Control, data=dat)
```

#Effect size formulation (random-effect/ REML) and heterogeneity test

```
meta <- rma(yi, vi, data=dataset, method="REML")
summary(meta, digits=3)
```

#Publication bias test

```
funnel(meta)
regtest(meta, predictor= "sei")
```

#SUBGROUP ANALYSIS

#Moderator dose (continuous)

```
dose_linear <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ dose, data=dataset)
summary(dose_linear, digits=3)
dose_quadratic <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ dose + I(dose^2), data=dataset)
summary(dose_quadratic, digits=8)
```

#moderator duration (numerical)

```
dura <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ 0 + duration, data=dataset)
summary(dura, digits=3)
```

#moderator initial age (numerical)

```
age <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ 0 + age, data=dataset)
summary(age, digits=3)
```

#moderator initial form (numerical)

```
form <- rma(yi, vi, mods = ~ 0 + form, data=dataset)
summary(form, digits=3)
```